

EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL ADVERTISING WITH MACHINE LEARNING IN BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF YOUNG CONSUMERS

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Article Info

Received : 10 Feb 2026
Revised: 28-Feb-2026
Accepted : 28 Apr 2026
Published online: 15-May-2026

Cite This Article As

Corpus D Cor Jesu F & P.Manivannan (2026), "Effectiveness of Digital Advertising with Machine Learning in Buying Behaviour of Young Consumers", International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, Volume 13, Issue 1, 2026, pp 52-59. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20193951>

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ABSTRACT

The growing synergy between machine learning (ML) and the evolving domain targeted advertising has created transformative shift in the way businesses interact with customers. In today's competitive market place organisations can no longer afford to adopt generalised marketing strategies; instead, they are increasingly turning towards machine learning algorithms to design digital advertising. The rapid growth of digital advertising has underscored in purchasing behaviour of customers. Digital advertising has become deeply intertwined with machine learning particularly when analysing purchasing behaviour of young consumers. The young consumers more active in social media comparing with traditional media like television, radio and newspapers. Because young customers are familiar with digital platforms, data-driven marketing strategies can best target them. Because it makes it possible for businesses to provide goods and services that are individualized to each customer, digital advertising has emerged as the predominant strategy.

The study examines effectiveness of digital advertising with integration of machine learning (ML) technologies or systems in influencing buying behaviour of young consumers. This study used descriptive research which relies on secondary data sources. It includes academic journals and scholarly publications which related to digital marketing, digital advertising, artificial intelligence and consumer behaviour. 30 peer reviewed studies published between 2018 to 2025 were reviewed using content analytics and thematic analytics. Findings of the study reveal that machine learning technologies has influence significantly to enhance digital advertising through personalised advertising content, customer segmentation, predictive models. These enable businesses and organisations to have better understand consumer preference.

Key words: Digital Advertising, Machine Learning, Consumer Behaviour, Young Consumer

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing synergy between machine learning (ML) and the evolving domain targeted advertising has created transformative shift in the way businesses interact with customers. In

today's competitive market place organisations can no longer afford to adopt generalised marketing strategies; instead, they are increasingly turning towards machine learning algorithms to design digital advertising. The rapid growth of digital advertising has underscored in purchasing behaviour of customers. Digital advertising has become deeply intertwined with machine learning particularly when analysing purchasing behaviour of young consumers. The young consumers more active in social media comparing with traditional media like television, radio and newspapers.

Because young customers are familiar with digital platforms, data-driven marketing strategies can best target them. Because it makes it possible for businesses to provide goods and services that are individualized to each customer, digital advertising has emerged as the predominant strategy. Machine learning, it is a sub segment of artificial intelligence (AI) that empower systems to process vast datasets, learn from patterns, and adapt to changing consumer behavior, is the driving force behind this trend. Young consumers namely Generation Z and millennial are most active consumers in digital media platforms.

They heavily depend on online for communication, entertainment and decision making on Purchases. The usage of smart phones and social networking applications has designed an environment where consumers are exposed to digital advertisements constantly. Digital advertising used to promotional information through online channels name called websites, search engines, social media platforms, mobile applications and email marketing systems. These digital platforms help organisations to reach consumers more effectively. It provides gateway for targeted communication based on consumer behaviour and preferences.

Machine Learning algorithms can be predictive based on historical data consumer behaviour which helps marketers to anticipate future consumer behaviour. Browsing History, Purchase records and social media interactions analyzed by algorithms to determine the likelihood that a consumer will make purchase of products or services. Based on the insight's businesses can deliver most relevant advertisements through proper channel at the right time. The growing importance ML in digital advertising pointing out the essence of academic research examining its impact on consumer behaviour. It is important to know how machine learning-driven strategies influence the buying behaviour of young consumers is most important because young people represent major portion of digital market. Therefore, this study aims to explore effectiveness of digital advertising with machine learning in buying behaviour of young consumers.

Machine Learning (ML)

The current era named as age of information it is not just because of humans have become data centric but also society has attained a level of maturity in analysing and getting source of information from data with artificial intelligence(AI) and machine learning(ML). The machine learning can be implemented when data analysis provides well-structured input. Educating in ML is part of mathematical point and it furnished by collaborating with inputs and outputs. Everything in ML revolves around algorithms. A structure or formula utilized to rectify the problem is called as algorithm.

Learning to solve problems with ML comes in many different methods based on the objective oriented and algorithms point of view. ML algorithm can be classified into three major groups named as supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning means predicting exact or more appropriate results from sample data which contain values in numeric, labels, tags etc. Unsupervised learning the term itself explains that algorithm need to understand from raw source of data which means the source of will be plain, it has to deliver results on its own way. Reinforcement quite similar to unsupervised learning in the sense it has to produce the algorithm with lack of data.

The following three algorithms which are used on machine learning namely NaiveBayes this algorithm is used predict get more accurate result from the data. This kind of algorithm used internet industry in order to find spam detection, texts from AI. Another algorithm Bayesian networks (graph form) it is used get result in the form of graph probability method followed as main stream. A decision tree helps to interpret symbols and their meanings. It defines decision making capacity of AI. In other words, to explain that it creates decisions like nested decision. Recommender system helps to detecting and recognizing the images, Chabot utilized to communicate with Machine language translation, Speech recognition, Behavioral planning for autonomous driving these are all Machine Learning Real-World Applications.

Statement of the Problem

In today's digital era consumers have plenty of information about product and services. It leads to more confusion to make proper decision on products. In order to rectify the issues businesses have implemented recommendation system with machine learning. With the intention of improving both the customer experience and the outcomes for the business, these systems aim to provide relevant product suggestions based on customer preferences, behavior, and history.

Despite the widespread use of recommendation systems by leading e-commerce and digital platforms, there is still limited empirical evidence on their actual influence on customer satisfaction and sales performance, particularly in varied market contexts and across different types of consumers. While some studies suggest that personalization enhances engagement and conversion rates, others raise concerns about over-personalization, privacy intrusions, and customer trust.

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand how Machine Learning (ML) supports Digital Advertising
2. To identify consumer behaviour on Digital Advertising with Machine Learning
3. To find impact of Digital Advertising

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Thomas et al (2020) have examined in the topic of "How artificial intelligence will change the future of marketing" the author anticipated a multidimensional framework for understanding the impact of AI in intelligence level, task types and whether AI is implanted in robot. This study made all three into single frame work. The authors highlighted policy

questions which are related to privacy, bias and ethics. Finally the authors concludes the study by stating that AI will create more effectiveness in marketing strategies and consumer behaviour if it is increase human managers rather than replaces.

Vanneesa et al (2022) have investigated “Machine Learning and Marketing: A systematic Literature Review”. This study reveals implementation of machine learning methods in marketing applications. The authors reviewed articles from the period of 2008-2022. In this mentioned period machine learning grown drastically. It includes deep learning, supervised learning, reinforcement learning and hybrid methods. In common maturity in the usage of ML in marketing was increasing. The authors finally discovered machine learning solved main marketing problems which were related with consumer behaviour, forecasting, customer segmentation.

Ibrahim Hali Efendioglu (2023) revealed in the topic of Trends in Artificial Intelligence Marketing A Bibliometric analysis”. The author examined publications which are related to artificial intelligence marketing. The data were analysed by utilizing R programming language, R studio and Bibliometrix package. The author analyzed from web of science and examined the period of 1983 to 2023. The study indicates that artificial intelligence gained significance in the year of 2015 and experienced more rapid increase in 2018. The author concludes by stating that AI will have an impact significantly in the field of marketing, marketers can driven by AI technologies have the vast opportunity to create competitiveness in business.

Chahana Joshi et al.(2025) examined in the topic of “Social Media Marketing and Consumer Behaviour”. This study focused on age, gender, employment and purchasing decisions. The author employed descriptive research method to evaluate how individuals across different demographics perceive and respond to social media marketing strategies. Convenience sampling method used for this study and conducted at kathamandu. The study reveals that there is no statistically relationship between demographic factors and purchasing decisions. The study suggested that social media marketing influences all consumer segments.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopts analytical method to analyse the digital advertising with machine learning technologies and consumer buying behaviour. In order to examining patterns and trends within existing data sources the descriptive research is most appropriate method.

Data Sources

The data collected from academic journals, conference proceedings and scholarly databases. It relies on secondary data sources. The selected data focused on digital advertising, machine learning and consumer behaviour in market.

Research articles published between 2018 and 2026 were included in this analysis. We considered only peer reviewed articles. The data selected based on relevance of digital marketing techniques and buying behaviour of consumer.

Data analysis and Interpretation

The study examined secondary data collected from published articles related to digital advertising, machine learning and consumer buying behaviour. A total of 30 peer-reviewed research articles published from 2018 to 2026 were selected from academic data sets including google scholar, Scopus and Science Direct.

The analysis was conducted using **Content Analysis and Thematic Analysis Techniques** to identify patterns and relationship between digital advertising strategies and consumer buying among young consumers.

4. CONTENT ANALYSIS

Table 1.1 Digital Advertising Platforms

Online Platform	Number of Studies	Percentage
Social Media Advertising	12	40%
Search Engine Advertising	06	20%
E-Commerce Advertising	07	23%
Mobile App Advertising	05	17%

The above Table indicates social media advertising are most frequently used digital advertising platform for targeting young consumers. Because the young consumers spend their significant time on digital platform especially social media. They are frequently exposed to personalised advertisement.

Table 1.2 Machine Learning Techniques used in Digital advertising

ML Techniques	Number of studies	Purpose of the study
Logistic Regression	06	Prediction of Purchase
Decision Tree	05	Consumer Classification
Random Forest	07	Prediction in Behaviour
K- Means Clustering	06	Customer Segmentation
Recommendation System	06	Personalised Advertising

The data selected for studies used some of the above ML techniques in that Random forecast and recommendation system are widely used techniques for analytics of prediction on consumer behaviour based on their purchase intension.

Table 1.3 Factors Influencing the Consumer Buying Behaviour

Factor Influence	Frequency	%
Personalised Advertising	20	67%
Consumer Engagement	18	60%
Targeted Advertising	16	53%
Product Recommendation	15	50%
Social Media Influence	14	47

Personalised advertising is the most influential factor which enhance consumer buying behaviour. ML algorithms helps business to deliver tailor made advertisement to the targeted consumer based on individual preference and purchase intension.

5. THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Personalised Digital Advertising

Consumer data analysed by Machine Learning algorithms to create most attractive advertisement based on consumer interest. The advertisements created to match the preference of consumer and make them to influence in buying decision.

Consumer Analytics in Predictive Models

Consumer behaviour can be forecast by using predictive models, it analysis the browsing patterns, purchase history and demographic characteristics of the consumer. The buying behaviour or purchase decision can be much more in clear cut point.

Consumer Engagement via Interactive Content

Videos, influencer marketing and social media campaigns these are called interactive advertising formats. This makes the more consumer engagement. In other words to explain consumer engagement is influenced by interactive content style.

Data- Driven Marketing Strategies

Businesses are now mostly rely on Machine Learning techniques or systems it designs the marketing strategies by using real time consumer data. In order to the influence the consumer the organisations more widely technological support to promote product and services.

6. CONCLUSION

The implementation of Digital Advertising with machine learning has significantly transformed the path business to communicate with consumers. It helps organisations to analyse larger datasets in order to discover consumer behaviour patterns and improve campaigns personalised advertising. It is more effective comparing with the traditional methodologies. This study examined effectiveness of digital advertising with machine learning in influencing young consumers on their buying behaviour using secondary data. The results explained that personalised advertising, predictive analytics and targeted marketing strategies are influenced and increased the buying intension in other words to define buying behaviour or purchase decision. Organisations that invest in machine learning systems to promote and develop their innovative marketing strategies and to maintain competitive advantage in the present digital market place.

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